

Report of the CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6 Task Force

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1. Introduction

Over the past decade, the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) has emerged as one of the milestone initiatives of the regional climate modelling community. Despite this progress, an imbalance still persists across CORDEX regions in terms of research activity, data availability, and scientific coverage. Some regions benefit from extensive modeling capacity, long-term institutional collaboration, and rich observational datasets, while others continue to face significant resource and data limitations. This uneven distribution poses challenges for achieving a truly coordinated global framework, as inconsistencies in methodological approaches, ensemble coverage, and data accessibility can constrain cross-regional comparison and synthesis. As an example, the simulations plans available, completed or planned for the next CMIP6 downscaling phase are summarised in Figure 1.

a

b

Figure 1: Number of published (blue), completed (black), running (green) and planned (red) simulations in the 9 CORDEX domains considered by the CORE experiment. Panel **a** summarises

*the simulations considering all the SSP scenarios and panel **b** is specific for the SSP3-7.0 scenario.*

If we consider all the SSP scenarios (panel a) or only the SSP3-7.0 the huge imbalance is evident among CORDEX domains, with AUS and EUR with the major number of planned, in progress or completed simulations, followed by SEA, NAM and EAS with a much smaller number, and several domains (CAM, SAM, and AFR) with almost no simulations.

To answer these needs, the first CORDEX-Coordinated Output for Regional Evaluations (CORDEX-CORE; Giorgi et al., 2022) experiment has been initiated, which has proven to be highly successful in producing a comprehensive and valuable dataset encompassing all land regions of the world. This dataset has significantly enriched the scientific literature, enabling detailed assessments of regional climate processes, variability, and extremes (Teichmann et al. 2020; Coppola et al., 2021; Giorgi et al 2022). Moreover, the CORE experiment made a major contribution to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), particularly in the Regional Climate Change assessments. It provided a large fraction of the total CORDEX simulations featured in the IPCC Interactive Atlas (<https://interactive-atlas.ipcc.ch/>; Gutiérrez et al., 2021), which has since been adopted as a supported product of COPERNICUS (Diez-Sierra et al., 2022).

Building on this success, this Task Force has been established to address the remaining challenges and to further enhance coordination, consistency, and integration within the CORDEX framework.

2. Overarching Goals

The Task Force has developed and implemented a standardized unified protocol to ensure the creation of consistent and balanced downscaled climate ensembles synchronized with each new cycle of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP). This will guarantee methodological consistency, facilitate comparison across regions, and strengthen the link between global and regional modeling efforts. The CORDEX-CORE protocol will be based on the CORDEX protocol and the expertise from the domains and will aim to balance the distribution of regional climate projections among all the land regions of the world. CORDEX-CORE is complementary to domain-specific activities and will take into account the domain tailored needs through an open and inclusive process by which the CORDEX POCs are invited to participate and contribute.

In this way the cooperation among CORDEX communities will be enhanced to tackle shared scientific questions, such as the analysis of mean climate conditions, variability, extreme events, and associated hazards. Moreover, themes that span multiple regions, including monsoon systems, tropical and extratropical cyclones, and teleconnection patterns can be approached in a coordinated regional way. By encouraging collaborative studies, joint analyses, and coordinated experiments, the work that will be done thanks to this Task Force (TF) will create a more interconnected scientific environment capable of addressing complex, transboundary climate phenomena.

Another essential goal of the TF is to strengthen global linkages by working to build stronger connections with major international modeling initiatives, including CMIP, the High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HiResMIP), and the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP). These partnerships are essential to ensure that CORDEX outputs are integrated into global climate assessments and that regional findings inform broader impact modeling and adaptation frameworks.

The TF will support and complement other CORDEX Task Forces focused on Machine Learning-based downscaling, Regional Ocean Climate Projections, and Convection-Permitting Modeling. This integration will help ensure that advancements in methodology, technology, and scientific understanding are shared across Task Forces, thereby maximizing efficiency and innovation within the CORDEX ecosystem.

Through these actions, the Task Force aims to advance the CORDEX mission of providing high-quality, policy-relevant regional climate information that supports adaptation planning, risk assessment, and sustainable development. By fostering stronger scientific collaboration, harmonizing methodologies, and linking regional and global modeling communities, this initiative represents a crucial step toward a more balanced, coordinated, and impactful CORDEX framework.

In the following sections the summary of the work flow of the past year will be reported as well as the draft of the simulations protocol, Recommendations and timeline of implementation.

3. Work flow

The Task Force was launched in October 2024 with a one year mandate to initiate exploratory activities and assess potential directions for future work.

3.1 Task Force Members

In the first months of TF activity a call of interest was circulated among all the CORDEX POCs, previous members of the CORE1 initiative, and Flagship Pilot Studies (FPS) community relevant for this task. Table 1 reports all members that were following the work flow evolution of the TF.

Table 1: CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6 Task Force Members

Name	Institution/domain and/or expertise
Erika Coppola coordinator	ICTP, Trieste, Italy/ SAT - RCM - emulators
Claas Teichmann coordinator	GERICS, Hamburg, Germany / RCM
Shabeh ul Hasson	University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany/ RCM
Moetasim Ashfaq	ORNL, USA / RCM
Shaukat Ali	POC Central Asia - ESD
Melissa Bukovsky	Univ. of Wyoming, USA / SAT - RCM - ESD
Tereza Cavazos	CICESE, Mexico / SAT - RCM / CMIP Core Panel
Marianna Adinolfi	CMCC, Italy / RCM
Jesús Fernandez	IFCA, Santander, Spain / SAT - RCM
Erasmus Buonomo	UKMO / RCM

Adam Jaczewski	IMWM, Warsaw, Poland
Ozan Mert Göktürk	NORCE, Bergen, Norway / RCM
Maria Laura Bettolli	University of Buenos Aires, Argentina / ESD
Rosmeri Porfirio da Rocha	USP, Brazil / RCM
George Zittis	CYI, Nicosia, Cyprus
Sushant Das	NIT Rourkela, India / RCM
Tannecia Stephenson	UWI, Jamaica / RCM
Eun-Soon IM	HKUST, Hong Kong / RCM
Chris Lennard	UCT, South Africa / RCM
Grigory Nikulin	SMHI, Sweden / RCM
Samuel Somot	CNRM, Météo-France, Toulouse, France / RCM
Jason Evans	UNSW, Sydney, Australia / SAT - RCM
Christian Steger	DWD, Offenbach, Germany / RCM
Xuejie Gao	IAP, China / RCM

3.2 Modus Operandi

The TF started to work with a first kick-off meeting at the end of 2024 that has been followed by monthly meetings for a total of 9 meetings. The first action was the establishment of a TF e-mail list (cordex-core-tf@listserv.dfn.de) to make the communications faster and more inclusive. Most of the work is dedicated to the discussion and definition of a GCM selection strategy followed by a decision on the protocol to be adopted in the CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 and to serve as reference and starting point for the next CORE-CMIP phases.

4. Selection of GCMs

The GCM selection strategy has been carried forward in collaboration with the Task Force on preparation of CORDEX-CMIP7. The aim was to develop a well-documented procedure to come to some final conclusion and propose a way forward.

The goal was to suggest the minimum best matrix from which to select three GCMs that are best performing in all domains for present climate and are covering, as much as possible, all ranges of future projections in all the regions for each domain in terms of temperature and precipitation. Three GCMs will be recommended with three additional GCMs as backup in case one of the recommended GCMs doesn't perform well in a specific region. The need to cover 9 domains in combination with limited computer resources and the urgent timing for data delivery lead to this constrained choice.

To determine the GCM selection criteria, a survey among all the participants to the TF and the POC representative has been launched and a preliminary paper documenting the model selection criteria is in preparation following previous work (Ashfaq et al, 2022; Grose et al., 2023; Arias et al. 2025; Di Virgilio et al., 2025; Andrade Cardoso et al., 2025, Sobolowski et al. 2025, Somot et al. 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8207473>) . This will serve as a prototype of the model selection protocol for this CMIP phase and the following ones.

A multi-criteria framework was developed to select global climate models (GCMs) for CORDEX CORE-CMIP6 downscaling. It evaluated models based on five main aspects: historical performance, model independence, effective future climate sensitivity, precipitation spread, and data availability. The goal was to select models that are physically credible, diverse, and practical for regional downscaling, while using the same subset across all CORDEX domains for consistency.

Model evaluation involved both historical and future simulations. Historical performance was assessed for the period 1981–2014 using 45 CMIP6 models, with ERA5 reanalysis as the reference. The evaluation used key variables such as near-surface air temperature, precipitation, sea level pressure, winds, humidity, and sea surface temperature. Future projections for 2015–2100 under the SSP3–7.0 scenario were analyzed to assess climate sensitivity (based on projected temperature change) and precipitation spread (based on inter-model variability). Only 31 models had the required data for this future evaluation. All data were regridded to a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid, and analyses were conducted for nine CORDEX domains subdivided into IPCC AR6 regions to ensure regional consistency (Figure 1).

which measures systematic offsets in magnitude relative to the observed variability; and normalized spatially centered root mean square error (RMSE), which estimates total spatial deviation relative to the observed spatial variability. For spatial RMSE, normalization was based on the spatial standard deviation of the reference dataset, whereas for bias, normalization was based on the temporal standard deviation. These scores were averaged to produce a single performance score per metric. Figure 2 provides an example of skill scores over Africa and aggregated details across all CORDEX domains.

Table 2: Unique metrics used for the regional and global aggregated evaluation

African Easterly Jet	HUS850 DJF	SAM MTG	TAS Peak Month
Atlantic ITCZ ¹	HUS850 JJA	SAM U_SHEAR	TAS SD
AUS Monsoon Demise	Indian Ocean Dipole	SAM V_SHEAR	TAS SON
AUS Monsoon Onset	Mascarene High	SAS Monsoon Demise	TOS DJF
AUS MTG ²	Mozambique Channel Trough	SAS Monsoon Lows Index	TOS JJA
AUS U ³ _SHEAR	NAM Monsoon Demise	SAS Monsoon Onset	TOS SON
AUS V ⁴ _SHEAR	NAM Monsoon Onset	SAS MTG	U200 DJF
Azores High	NAM MTG	SAS U_SHEAR	U200 JJA
CA Precipitation Bimodality	NAM U_SHEAR	SAS V_SHEAR	U850 DJF
Caribbean Low-level Jet	NAM V_SHEAR	SEA Monsoon Demise	U850 JJA
EAF Low-level Jet	NAO	SEA Monsoon Onset	V200 DJF
EAF Monsoon Demise	North Atlantic Polar Jet	SEA MTG	V200 JJA
EAF Monsoon Onset	PR ⁵ Amplitude	SEA U_SHEAR	V850 DJF
EAF MTG	PR DJF	SEA V_SHEAR	V850 JJA
EAF U_SHEAR	PR Hovmöller	SEAF Monsoon Demise	WAF Monsoon Demise
EAF V_SHEAR	PR JJA	SEAF Monsoon Onset	WAF Monsoon Onset
EAS Monsoon Demise	PR MAM	SEAF MTG	WAF MTG
EAS Monsoon Onset	PR Peak Month	SEAF U_SHEAR	WAF U_SHEAR
EAS MTG	PR Relative Entropy	SEAF V_SHEAR	WAF V_SHEAR
EAS Subtropical Westerly Jet	PR SD	South Atlantic High	Wang Index
EAS U_SHEAR	PR Seasonality	Subtropical Westerly Jet	Western Pacific Subtropical High
EAS V_SHEAR	PR SON	TAS6 Amplitude	ZG500 DJF

EAS Winter Monsoon Index	Southern Annular Mode	TAS DJF	ZG500 JJA
ENSO Niño-3.4	SAM Monsoon Demise	TAS JJA	
Guo Index	SAM Monsoon Onset	TAS MAM	

ITCZ¹ = Intertropical Convergence Zone, MTG2 = Meridional Temperature Gradient, U3=Zonal Winds, V⁴ = Meridional Winds, PR⁵ = Precipitation, TAS⁶ = Surface Temperature

Figure 2. Illustration of the models' performance across evaluation metrics. (Top) The heatmap shows unweighted skill scores of CMIP6 GCMs over Africa. The bar plot shows the spread in skill across models. (Bottom) Aggregated summary of GCMs skill across CORDEX domains for unweighted metrics. The colored annulus shows the interquartile range of mean model skill across all metrics, with the median marked as a solid line. Outer radial spokes highlight the ten metrics with the lowest mean skill. The dot position denotes the mean model skill for that metric, the spoke length represents its deviation from the domain median ($|\text{mean} - \text{median}|$), and the dot size indicates inter-model standard deviation (spread in skill). Reference circles and N correspond to skill values of 0 and 100, and the number of evaluated metrics, respectively.

To avoid redundancy, each metric within an AR6 region was assigned a weight based on its uniqueness relative to the others, giving greater importance to independent metrics. The weighting approach follows the method developed by Ashfaq et al. (2022). Pairwise Pearson correlations are first computed among all metrics within each AR6 domain, and these correlations are converted into a correlation-based distance measure, where smaller distances indicate stronger relationships between metrics. A similarity score is then calculated for each metric pair within a specified similarity radius of 0.2. This threshold emphasizes strong inter-metric relationships while allowing for the moderate correlations expected among interconnected climate variables. The effective redundancy of a metric is defined as the sum of its similarity scores with all other metrics, and the inverse of this effective redundancy provides the metrics weight. Metrics that are largely independent from others receive higher weights, while those showing strong interdependence are proportionally down weighted. Figure 3 illustrates the weighting framework, showing how metric correlations, similarity scores, and resulting weights are related.

Figure 3. Illustration of the interrelationships among performance metrics across AR6 regions. (A) Pairwise correlations (left triangle), similarity scores (right triangle), and overall metric scores (line plot) are shown for one AR6 region (SWS) within South America (SAM). **(B)** Kernel Density Estimate (KDE) of global pairwise correlations across all AR6 regions within the nine CORDEX domains. **(C)** Relationship between similarity and absolute correlation for all model–metric pairs. Hexagonal binning represents the joint density of points; the gray line

indicates the median similarity in bins of |correlation|, and the orange line shows the aggregated (maximum) pair weight applied in the analysis. Marginal KDEs along the top and right axes display the individual distributions of |correlation| and similarity, respectively.

Weighted skill scores were subsequently averaged across all AR6 regions to obtain domain-level performance scores. Finally, global ranks were based on the averaging of nine CORDEX domain-level scores. Figure 4 provides a summary of models global skill scores and across nine CORDEX domains.

GCM Ranks by Domain and Global (models sorted by global rank)

Figure 4. Models rank across nine CORDEX domains and globally.

Model independence was evaluated to quantify the structural diversity of the GCM ensemble. Independence reflects how distinct models are in representing climate system processes—high independence implies unique physical behavior, whereas low independence indicates redundancy due to shared components or parameterizations. Independence was quantified using pairwise cosine similarity computed from standardized index scores across all metrics and AR6 regions within the nine CORDEX domains. The results are summarized in the dendrogram shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. **The dendrogram illustrates interdependence among GCMs.** The height of each branch represents the distance between two models, with smaller values indicating greater similarity. A distance ≤ 0.1 is used as a threshold for identifying models that are effectively redundant. Models shown in green include data for the future evaluation period.

Effective climate sensitivity, defined as the apparent responsiveness of a climate model to increasing greenhouse gas (GHG) forcing over a specified future period under realistic, scenario-driven conditions (for example, SSP3-7.0), and precipitation projection spread were calculated regionally as averages over land-only AR6 regions within each CORDEX domain. These regional values were then averaged across the CORDEX domains to derive global sensitivities and precipitation spread. The overall results are summarized in a global Sankey

diagram (Figure 6) that integrates these metrics together with model ranking and inter-model independence to illustrate the framework used for model selection.

Figure 6. Global Sankey diagram summarizing the four criteria of the model selection framework: historical performance, inter-model independence, effective future climate sensitivity, and precipitation projection spread. The left nodes represent 45 CMIP6 models, each labeled by its global rank. The top 14 models lack SSP3-7.0 data and are therefore used only to establish the relative ranking of the remaining models. For the 31 models with SSP3-7.0 projections, the middle nodes correspond to Δ TAS tercile bins representing low, mid, and high warming, while the right nodes show per-model Δ PR bins indicating dry ($< -5 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$), mid (within $\pm 5 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$), and wet ($> +5 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$) conditions during the last 30 years of the 21st century. Colored rectangles beside bottom 31 model labels denote their relative independence: models sharing the same color have cosine similarity ≥ 0.9 , while those shown in black have cosine similarity < 0.9 and are considered relatively independent.

Based on the above criteria of present day evaluation and regional future spread of projections the minimum best matrix proposed for the CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 phase is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Minimum GCM matrix for CMIP6 downscaling

Climate Sensitivity	GCM 1st choice	GCM 2nd choice
Low	NorESM2-MM	MPI-ESM1-2-LR
Medium	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	CNRM-ESM2-1
High	EC-Earth3-Veg	UKESM1-0

5. Simulation Protocol

The CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6 protocol is based on the [CORDEX-CMIP6 experiment design](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268192) (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15268192), is inspired by CORDEX-CORE phase 1 experiment described in the [CORDEX-CORE Experiment I special issue](#) (Giorgi et al, 2021) and complements the CORDEX-CMIP6 downscaling plans (available at <https://wcrp-cordex.github.io/simulation-status/>) with a more consistent and balanced set of RCMs and driving GCMs.

To avoid repetition we highlight here the differences between the current protocol and the one of CORDEX-CMIP6 according to the discussions and the decisions taken during the TF lifetime. This helps to maintain the consistency with the original CORDEX-CMIP6 protocol and also to highlight the special setup of CORDEX-CORE-CMIP6.

5.1 Resolution/Grid-spacing

The resolution for all domains has been set to 0.11° (~12.5 km). The rationale of the choice is the overall trend toward higher-resolution experiments across several major initiatives like CMIP7, HighResMIP and DestinE. Increasing the resolution is therefore essential to remain consistent with the evolving modeling landscape and to guarantee detailed climate information over all the land populated regions that are not yet adequately covered by other projects. This level of detail is also crucial for providing information that can effectively support policy-relevant decisions.

If groups cannot afford it, 0.16° (18km) or 0.22° (25 km) are the backup resolutions, limited to problematic domains for specific RCMs.

5.2 Model complexity and consistency across domains

Model complexity and consistency has to be tailored to get optimal results for each regional domain, supporting follow-up research and enabling deriving climate information for applications for Vulnerability, Impacts, Adaptation and Climate Services (VIACS). This implies that there is no strict requirement to use exactly the same model configuration across all domains, but adjustments in the model setup and its parameterizations are allowed. These changes should of course be transparent and documented in the meta data and/or the corresponding papers and other documentation resources. Urban parameterization is strongly encouraged if available.

To sum up, the model version should be the same across domains, but the model configuration can be domain dependent.

5.3 Evaluation experiment

In CORDEX-CORE the evaluation experiment has been set to be mandatory and it follows the CMIP6 CORDEX protocol.

GHG forcing

The observed greenhouse gas information will be used.

Land use/Land cover

Static land cover will be used in CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 but further revisions may be possible in future CORDEX-CORE phases, to implement the evolving LULC upon agreement of a minimum number of RCMs.

Aerosols

Modeling groups are strongly encouraged to use a time- and space-variant aerosol dataset in their simulations, instead of a static dataset. Mean monthly aerosol values are sufficient. The minimum requirement is to use the AOD550 parameter.

The MERRA-2 reanalysis has been selected (1st EURO-CORDEX workshop and 12th EURO-CORDEX GA) as the reference aerosol product to be implemented. The aerosol dataset is available to the community through the [EU-DAT portal](#) (Vol 1: 1980.01-1994.11, Vol2: 1994.12-2000.05, Vol3: 2000.05-2015.03, Vol4: 2015.04-2021.01) . The meta data (including spectral intervals) are described in volume 1. Currently aerosol data are only for the visible band, soon more bands will be added. More details provided in (<https://cordex.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/aerosol4cordex.pdf>).

As different modeling systems implement aerosols in a different way, modelers with questions on the implementation of aerosols can contact the EURO-CORDEX PoCs.

Spectral nudging

The application of spectral nudging should be guided by community consensus within each RCM group. Choices should be documented.

5.4 Historical experiments

Land use/Land cover

Static land cover will be used in CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 but further revisions may be possible in future CORDEX-CORE phases, to implement the evolving LULC upon agreement of a minimum number of RCMs.

Aerosol

Modeling groups are required to apply the aerosol trend and space-time variations of the coupled GCM (or other aerosol data that follows the observed historical trend). Mean monthly aerosol values are sufficient. The minimum requirement is to use the AOD550 parameter.

Spectral nudging

The application of spectral nudging should be guided by community consensus within each RCM group. Choices should be documented.

5.5 Scenario experiments

Boundary conditions from the CMIP6 ScenarioMIP are available for 2015–2100. The prioritized scenarios are SSP3-7.0 and SSP1-2.6, followed by SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5. The minimum requirement is to downscale the highest scenario (i.e., SSP3-7.0) to cover all global warming levels within the three selected GCMs followed by downscaling the three GCMs for SSP1-2.6.

GHG forcing

RCM groups should use the same scenario GHG forcing as in the driving CMIP6 models (Meinshausen et al. 2019).

Land use/Land cover

Static land cover will be used in CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 but further revisions may be possible in future CORDEX-CORE phases, to implement the evolving LULC upon agreement of a minimum number of RCMs.

Aerosol

Modeling groups are strongly encouraged to apply the aerosol trend and space-time variations of the driving GCM (or aerosol data with behavior following a selected SSP). Mean monthly aerosol values are sufficient. The minimum requirement is to use the AOD550 parameter.

Spectral nudging

The application of spectral nudging should be guided by community consensus within each RCM group. Choices should be documented.

5.6 RCM Documentation

Climate model documentation, providing all necessary details on model configurations, experiments, etc., is an integral part of climate modeling activities. Currently, a free format is assumed. As an example the modelling groups can be referred to the [EURO-CORDEX CMIP6 RCM component description](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8388779) (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8388779) or the [machine-readable documentation](https://med-cordex.github.io/model-documentation) (https://med-cordex.github.io/model-documentation) of Med-CORDEX.

5.7 Output variables

The output variables to be saved are provided in the CORDEX-CMIP6 data request¹. They are a subset of the default data request, considering the amount of storage that is required.

1

https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/data-request-table/blob/cordex-core/data-request/dreq_CORDEX-CORE.csv

The final list is available at <https://github.com/WCRP-CORDEX/data-request-table/pull/57>.

5.8 Archiving and publishing specifications

CORDEX-CORE simulations shall be published on the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF) to be consistent with the CMIP6 archive and to make the output available to as many users as possible. All simulations will be formatted according to the CORDEX archive specifications that provide technical aspects of CORDEX data format and guidance for publishing CORDEX data on ESGF².

5.9 Domains

In Table 3 the models that are currently involved in the CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 are reported with the 3 different options listed to participate in the CORDEX-CORE experiment. The 9 domains participating in the CORDEX-CORE experiment are reported in Figure 1.

Table 3: List of RCM models that participate to the CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 according to the different options

9 out of 9 domains (Figure 7)	7* out of 9 domains
RegCM5, REMO,	HadREM3-GA7-05, WRF

*This reduced domain number protocol is supposed to produce simulation for only one domain among : Europe, North America and Australasia

² Nikulin et al. (2025). CORDEX-CMIP6 Archiving Specifications for Dynamical Downscaling (Version v2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15047096>

Figure 7: The 9 CORDEX-CORE domains (NAM, CAM, SAM, EUR, AFR, WAS, EAS, SEA, AUS) selected for the CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 experiment. Consistently with the previous phase the CAS domain is not included in CORDEX-CORE (Giorgi et al., 2021).

6. Proposed actions

The CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 simulations should start as soon as possible to have the evaluation experiment ready by the end of summer 2026 to be reported in the CORDEX-CORE Special Issue paper. The scenario simulations should be ready by Sept-Oct 2026 and the data accessibility should be illustrated and discussed in the Trieste WS, to have enough time to plan the scientific papers that will contribute to the AR7 WGI. The CORE simulations will also serve as a basis for the ML training and downscaling as well as to the RCM-CP simulations.

CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 TF timeline

Figure 10: CORDEX-CORE implementation timeline

The CORDEX-CORE CMIP6 activity should be continued in a new CORDEX-CORE CMIP7 one to not lose the momentum and opportunity to be better aligned in time with the new CMIP7 cycle in collaboration with the newly established CORDEX CMIP7 Task Team.

Both CORDEX-CORE activities should serve and complement the CORDEX ML based emulator downscaling activity

The CORDEX-CORE Task Force activity should evolve toward having a specific Regional Earth System Model framework with an homogenous number of projections at a resolution approaching the km-scale resolution.

To accomplish all the above action the launch of a CORDEX-CORE Task Team is recommended with an initial duration of two years.

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